

CHARACTERISTICS OF AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING ACTIVITY

N.M.Quchqorova

Oriental University p.f.d., Professor

Ibrohimova Iroda

Student of Oriental University

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Annotation: This article describes the innovative approach of the teacher to the educational process: acmeological, axiological, creative and reflexive.

Keywords: acmeology, axiology, creativity, reflection, education, Innovation approach literacy process

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны инновационные подходы педагога к образовательному процессу: акмеологический, аксиологический, творческий и рефлексивный.

Ключевые слова: акмеология, аксиология, креативность, рефлексия, воспитание, начальная школа, инновационный подход.

Today, the task of school pedagogical communities is not limited to teaching and educating students, but also includes delivering knowledge through innovative approaches. The kind of individual the younger generation becomes in the future depends on the solid knowledge and upbringing they receive at school. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, emphasized: *“We have set as our main goal the creation of the foundation for a new Renaissance in Uzbekistan — the Third Renaissance — through large-scale democratic reforms, including educational reforms”* [1, p. 205]. Achieving this goal requires implementing reforms in the continuous education system and ensuring that the knowledge given in childhood is strong and thorough, preparing students to withstand future challenges.

Along with fundamental changes in the education system, innovative requirements are also imposed on individuals who carry out the educational process. For a teacher to engage in innovative activity, they must understand the essence of educational reforms and transition from traditional teaching methods to modern, innovation-based approaches. If we understand the essence of pedagogical technology, a teacher’s innovative activity can be characterized by the following components:

- 1.Acmeology
- 2.Axiology
- 3.Creativity
- 4.Reflection

Let us analyze these in relation to a teacher's professional activity.

Acmeology implies viewing the teaching profession as the highest value and recognizing students as the most valuable participants in the educational process. Indeed, no other profession offers the opportunity to work with such pure-hearted and sincere children as teaching does. A teacher should not forget that they can be both the subject and the object of the educational process.

Axiology refers to the system of values. A teacher is a person who is never forgotten by professionals of any field—academics, scientists, craftsmen, doctors, and others. The teacher's work plays a crucial role in shaping the lives of future generations.

Creativity involves a creative approach to teaching. Only when a teacher approaches each lesson creatively can they achieve their goals in a short time, increase students' interest in the learning process, and identify talented learners. A lesson can be considered a work of art. Through creative activity, teachers can help students achieve the outcomes defined by state educational standards. For this, teachers must effectively use interactive methods, appropriate tools, and modern pedagogical technologies.

Reflection means “looking back” or self-analysis. A teacher can achieve positive results only by continuously analyzing their educational activities. In this regard, it is useful to consider the words of K.D. Ushinsky:

“The art of education has a peculiar quality: it seems familiar and understandable to almost everyone, and to some it even appears easy. The less a person is acquainted with it theoretically and practically, the easier and clearer it seems.”

If a teacher does not organize reflection in the educational process, they cannot fully understand their achievements and shortcomings.

Future teachers are prepared for innovative activity through academic subjects and practical training at higher education institutions. Practicing teachers in schools develop their understanding of innovative activity, its goals, and objectives through professional development and continuous self-improvement. Therefore, every educator must be prepared for innovative activity both theoretically and practically, as this is a requirement of the modern era.

References:

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